

PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT OF GROUNDWATER POTENTIAL ZONES IN AYEDE EKITI, EKITI STATE, SOUTHWESTERN NIGERIA USING ELECTRICAL METHODS

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Abstract

An electrical resistivity survey was conducted at different locations within Ayede Ekiti, Ekiti State, Southwestern Nigeria. This is aimed at evaluating groundwater potential zones and aquifer properties within the study area. Data were acquired at nine different locations using the vertical electrical sounding method by employing the Schlumberger array configuration. This study utilizes resistivity data processed with IPI2win software to analyse the subsurface geology of a basement complex region. The result of the study showed that qualitatively, three major curve types (A, AH, HA, and H) were observed. Varying curve types, predominantly A curves, were observed across the research area, with notable groundwater potential indicated by H and HA curve types at select points. Through curve matching techniques, three to four distinct geo-electric layers were identified, while the quantitative interpretation resulted in deducing layer parameters of the topsoil, which has apparent resistivity values ranging from 37.5 to 450 ΩC and 0.56 to 8.22 ΩC for the topsoil. The second geo-electric layer, the lateritic zone, has apparent resistivity values ranging from 24.2 to 1262 m and a thickness of 1.63 to 19.2m. While the weathered basement has a resistivity and thickness of 249 to 541 m and 10.5 to 34.7 m. The fresh basement resistivity ranges from 156 to 8547 Ωm with infinity thickness. The weathered layer contributes to the aquifer. It was inferred that the VES 2, 3, and 6 regions are associated with high groundwater yield. The groundwater potential of VES 8 in the study area is inferred to be of moderate potential. However, VES 1, 4, 5, 7, and 9 are characterized by low groundwater potential. This research contributes valuable insights for geological mapping and groundwater resource assessment in complex basement terrains.

Keyword: Electrical Resistivity Survey, Groundwater Potential Zones, Ayede Ekiti.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increase in human population and agricultural activity in rural and urban areas has resulted in excessive groundwater abstraction to reach the intended goal [19]. Water has always been an essential resource for all living creatures, including humans. We use it to wash, fish, swim, drink, and cook, although not usually simultaneously [5]. [5] also claims that we are around two-thirds water and require it to survive. Water is required by all living creatures in some form or another. Humans have a top-priority demand for safe, high-quality water that is always available to suit both home and industrial needs, resulting in a global boom in water demand. Groundwater has a high potential for prospecting and exploration as a solution to the problem of limited availability of water for a variety of reasons. This has been a necessary and ever-increasing research desire to constantly alleviate this problem among humans.

An aquifer's utility as a groundwater source is determined by the porosity of the geologic stratum or layer from which it arose [8]. This aquifer function varies according to location, geological terrain, and other factors. To bridge the gap, in this work, a geophysical electrical resistivity survey employing vertical electrical sounding (VES) was utilized to systematically establish the value of the input parameter in assessing groundwater potential in Ayede Ekiti. As water shortages grow across the world, particularly in developing or third-world nations like Nigeria, the importance of access to water supplies cannot be overstated. Ayede Ekiti is one of the towns with poor pipe-borne water delivery systems [12]. Ayede Ekiti town is belong to basement complex location with a documented insufficient of water for agricultural and industrial growth [10, 11]. The present study involves the use of vertical electrical sounding to understand the hydrogeological condition of the study area [10, 11]. This will involve the determination of the thickness and resistivity of the subsurface layers, delineating the fracture zones, and establishing the depth of the bedrock, which will be done by governments, people, and non-governmental organizations to understand the features and nature of the aquifer in the area. This would aid in the provision of high-quality information on borehole placement for adequate water supply and the town's long-term growth.

2. THE STUDY AREA

The study area is Ayede metropolis, which is one of the towns linking Ekiti and Kwara States, Nigeria, and is bounded by latitudes 7°53'N and 7°54'N and longitudes 5°18'E and 5°22'E. The study area covers an area of about 52 km², with the surrounding communities of Imojo, Itaji, Ilafon, and Ishan Ekiti (Figure 1). There are insufficient pipe-borne water delivery systems in the town, resulting in an inadequate water supply. As a result, people rely on rainwater, surface water, and groundwater for home and agricultural purposes. The research region has a tropical climate and is covered with rain forests. The drainage is mainly dendritic, with hummocky and undulating terrain. The annual rainfall is around 1300 mm, and it is distributed bimodally throughout the hydrologic year. The first peak occurs between June and July, while the second peak occurs between September and October during the rainy season. The two wet seasons are normally separated by a draught (August break), while the dry season is defined by little or no rainfall between November and April [2].

Figure 1. Geological map of part of Ekiti State showing the Study Area. [2]

Figure 2. Location Map of the Study Area showing VES locations.

3. HYDROGEOLOGY OF THE STUDY AREA

The rocks of the basement complex terrain are highly impermeable and lack primary porosity, which refers to linked pore spaces produced during rock formation [7]. A rock's porosity and permeability contribute to its hydrogeologic qualities, which are then determined by the size, shape, and arrangement of the grains as well as the mineralogy of the rock [3]. The existence of cracks (secondary porosity), as well as the structure and thickness of the material covering the rocks, influence groundwater storage and potential [11, 14]. Fractures in rocks are mostly created by tectonic activity inside the crust. These are significant in basement rocks because they enhance weathering activity [6, 18]. The mineralogy of a rock type influences the degree of weathering. Rocks rich in ferromagnesian minerals and feldspars are subjected to a high degree of weathering, resulting in impermeable clay minerals, as opposed to silica-rich rocks, which provide permeable water-bearing sandy and gravely medium [4, 9]. The weathered layer and cracked basement are common locations for recoverable groundwater in the basement complex [1]. The detection and delineation of hydrogeological structure typically aid in the finding of groundwater potential zones in typical complicated environments [10, 18].

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.1. Field Work and Data Acquisition

A geophysical investigation involved the use of the electrical resistivity method at Ayede Ekiti. In which the vertical electrical sounding (VES) technique was used. A Schlumberger geoelectric sounding array, which is one of the most widely used configurations, in this case, the potential electrodes (MN) are closely spaced, while the current electrodes (AB) are increasingly spaced, such that $MN \leq AB/5$.

An ABEM terrameter and its accessories were used for data collection. This is to measure the resistance of the subsurface layers [17, 20]. The current electrode spacing (AB/2) ranges from 1-100 m, while the potential

electrode spacing (MN/2) ranges from 0.5 m to 16 m [13]. A total of nine VES points were probed over the entire area (Figure 2).

4.2. Computer Iteration Method

This method makes use of a geophysical program named IPI2win. The computer iteration procedure uses computer algorithms and inversion techniques to iteratively estimate the subsurface resistivity distribution based on apparent resistivity measurements. Curve matching becomes difficult when there are several layers; thus, computer iteration software simplifies the understanding of such situations. Field data was entered into the program for modeling. Modeling is the process of simulating the predicted apparent resistivity values for a given subsurface resistivity distribution. The apparent resistivity responses are computed using numerical techniques based on a theoretical model and the anticipated resistivity values of subsurface layers. The program generates synthetic data that would be anticipated if specific geological circumstances were true. The aim is to discover the best-fitting subsurface resistivity distribution that corresponds to the observed apparent resistivity data. This is an iterative procedure in which the computer changes the resistivity values in the original model to reduce the mismatch between the observed and anticipated apparent resistivity values. The technique allows for a maximum inaccuracy of less than 5%. This iteration aids in describing the curve types, which range from H to A, Q, QA, HA, and so on, as well as the number of layers and their apparent resistance.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A total of nine (9) VES locations were sounded within the research region, each employing a Schlumberger array setup. Tables 1 and 2 show the resistivity values obtained from VES locations investigated in the field (Figure 2).

5.1. Geo-electric Layers and Curve Types

The resistivity data obtained in the field were processed and evaluated using the geophysical software suite Ipi2win. This is done to identify the underlying layering (geoelectric layers), as well as their depth, thickness, and apparent resistivity values (Table 3). This method is known as curve matching [19]. The geo-electric layers (lithology with identical electrical resistivity values) in the research region as a basement complex geology exhibit three to four layers illustrating topsoil, lateritic zone, weathered basement, and fresh basement (Figure 3a-i). VES points 3 and 8 indicate four layers, whereas the remaining VES points show three layers. The curve types in the research region include A, AH, HA, and H curves, with the A curve being the most common (Table 3).

Table 1: Showing the Resistivity Data obtained from VES 1-5 on Field

AB/2	MN/2	VES 1	VES 2	VES 3	VES 4	VES 5
1	0.5	83.53	107.22	93.84	69.59	55.73
2	0.5	99.90	92.24	84.32	80.30	77.66
3	0.5	96.98	68.99	80.58	103.20	92.74
4	0.5	103.04	53.78	83.44	121.64	85.95
6	0.5	112.53	36.42	95.23	69.78	15.27
6	1	103.48	67.29	82.00	134.59	116.49
8	1	106.56	79.82	104.55	192.01	122.65
10	1	111.37	97.23	140.12	252.90	146.24
10	2	98.17	72.73	157.08	157.08	118.60
15	2	103.55	77.05	213.82	268.61	47.36
20	2	106.50	106.81	213.94	333.01	97.39
20	4	88.28	125.51	326.73	46.50	119.22
30	4	353.43	353.43	353.43	353.43	353.43
40	4	143.88	15858.76	319.19	426.63	157.71
40	8	55.92	5582.61	205.15	675.44	168.08
50	8	132.05	7333.66	272.43	760.85	204.69
60	8	206.40	7082.72	284.16	749.27	255.18
80	8	315.42	3204.42	356.88	857.03	312.90
80	16	303.48	2576.11	202.32	647.17	289.65
100	16	484.00	8639.38	290.60	844.30	315.14

Table 2: Showing the Resistivity Data obtained from VES 6-9 on Field

AB/2	MN/2	VES 6	VES 7	VES 8	VES 9
1	0.5	95.06	37.98	469.45	111.50
2	0.5	77.28	40.59	449.37	149.54
3	0.5	65.60	48.91	553.05	77.75
4	0.5	49.36	48.10	570.01	259.87
6	0.5	56.66	63.33	812.04	102.24
6	1	53.04	58.25	644.09	102.35
8	1	56.30	55.69	712.76	401.12
10	1	51.84	37.86	882.79	389.56
10	2	51.21	64.25	714.71	424.90
15	2	53.19	82.53	994.90	330.46
20	2	97.08	106.19	1218.94	263.89
20	4	84.51	108.86	1083.85	307.88
30	4	353.43	353.43	353.43	353.43
40	4	272.06	206.09	1294.34	45.24
40	8	205.46	269.55	741.42	85.14
50	8	281.27	347.54	908.12	292.07
60	8	364.74	436.84	770.48	344.24
80	8	531.56	390.81	1081.96	394.58
80	16	735.13	540.35	1030.44	407.15
100	16	1178.10	585.12	1315.54	519.34

Table 3: Summary of Geo-Electric Parameter Obtained

VES Number	Number of Layers	Resistivity (Ωm)	Aquifer Thickness (m)	Aquifer Depth (m)	Aquifer Layer (m)	Curve Type	Lithology's
VES 1	1	86.6	2.05	2.05	20.3	A	Top Soil
	2	142	18.2	20.3			Lateritic Soil
	3	474					Fresh Basement
VES 2	1	93.7	2.95	2.95	9.87	H	Top Soil
	2	48.7	6.92	9.87			Lateritic Soil
	3	962					Fresh Basement
VES 3	1	96.3	1.36	1.36	8.57	HA	Top Soil
	2	52.1	3.02	4.38			Lateritic Soil
	3	306	4.18	8.57			Weather Basement
	4	478					Fresh Basement
VES 4	1	71.2	1.95	1.95	5.2	A	Top Soil
	2	203	3.25	5.2			Lateritic Soil
	3	937					Fresh Basement
VES 5	1	78	8.22	8.22	27.4	A	Top Soil
	2	203	19.2	27.4			Lateritic Soil
	3	877					Fresh Basement
VES 6	1	92.7	2.15	2.15	6.75	H	Top Soil
	2	24.2	4.59	6.75			Lateritic Soil
	3	949					Fresh Basement
VES 7	1	37.5	1.97	1.97	20	A	Top Soil
	2	104	18	20			Lateritic Soil
	3	913					Fresh Basement
VES 8	1	450	2.63	2.63	49.3	AH	Top Soil
	2	1249	12	14.6			Lateritic Soil
	3	541	34.7	49.3			Weather Basement
	4	8547					Fresh Basement
VES 9	1	125	1.02	1.02	5.21	A	Top Soil
	2	167	4.19	5.21			Lateritic Soil
	3	503					Fresh Basement

Figure 3: (a) VES 1 showing A curve type, (b). VES 2 showing H curve type, (c). VES 3 showing H curve type, (d). VES 4 showing A curve type, (e). VES 5 showing A curve type, (f). VES 6 showing H curve type, (g). VES 7 showing A curve type, (h). VES 8 showing AH curve type, (i). VES 9 showing A curve type.

Vertical electrical soundings (VES) were randomly conducted at nine (9) distinct places within the study area and plotted using IPI2WIN software. The data were interpreted and explained as follows:

According to the interpretation, VES 1 is a curve with three geoelectric sections: topsoil, lateritic soil, and fresh basement. It may be deduced that it is not a suitable site for groundwater investigation.

As a H-curve type, VES 2 has three geoelectric sections: topsoil, lateritic soil, and fresh basement, according to Table 3 interpretations. This VES point indicates that there may be potential to explore for groundwater in lateritic soil at a depth of $2.95 \text{ m} \pm 6.92 \text{ m}$.

Topsoil, lateritic soil, weathered basement, and fresh basement are the four geoelectric sections that make up VES 3, a H and A curve type, according to Table 3. The VES point suggests that a weathered basement may have groundwater exploration potential, with a possible depth of $1.36 \text{ m} \pm 4.18 \text{ m}$.

Table 3 interprets VES 4, an A-type curve, as topsoil, lateritic soil, and fresh basement. Therefore, it may be concluded that groundwater exploration is not feasible at this location.

Table 3 interprets VES 5, an A-type curve, as topsoil, lateritic soil, and fresh basement. Therefore, it may be concluded that groundwater exploration is not feasible at this location.

As a H-curve type, VES 6 has three geoelectric sections: topsoil, lateritic soil, and fresh basement, according to Table 3 interpretations. This VES point indicates the possibility of exploring the groundwater at a depth of $2.15 \text{ m} \pm 4.59 \text{ m}$ within a weathered basement.

According to Table 3, VES 7, an A-type curve, corresponds to topsoil, lateritic soil, and fresh basement. Therefore, it may be concluded that groundwater exploration is not feasible at this location.

According to Table 3, VES 8, an A and H curve type, has four geoelectric sections: topsoil, lateritic soil, weathered basement, and fresh basement. This VES point indicates that a worn basement with a possible depth of $2.63 \text{ m} \pm 34.7 \text{ m}$ may be explored for groundwater.

Table 3 interprets VES 9, an A-type curve, as topsoil, lateritic soil, and fresh basement. Therefore, it may be concluded that groundwater exploration is not feasible at this location.

Summary of the curve-matched resistivity values Table 3 demonstrates that the topsoil has apparent resistivity values ranging from 37.5 to 450 Ωm with a thickness range of 0.56 to 8.22 m. The second geo-electric layer, the lateritic zone, has apparent resistivity values ranging from 24.2 to 1262 Ωm and a thickness of 1.63 to 19.2m. The third geo-electric layer, weathered basement, has resistivity values ranging from 249 to 541 Ωm and a thickness of 10.5 to 34.7m. The fresh basement's infinity geo-electric layer exhibits resistivity values ranging from 156 to 8547 Ωm and a thickness of infinity. The weathered layer is assessed to be aquiferous formations, which correspond to the aquifer in the research region, since it includes high-quality groundwater potential. The geo-electric parameters acquired in Table 3 were mathematically represented to determine different electric parameters. Tables 3 a show the range of values derived via curve matching.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The study area has nine (9) VES points, three (3) of which have a high potential for groundwater exploration (VES 2, 3, and 6), while VES 8 has a moderate potential for groundwater exploration. However, VES 1, 4, 5, 7, and 9 do not have potential for groundwater exploration in the study area, so 50% of the VES points are potential areas for groundwater exploration.

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